

Tracing traditions: An analytical study of Late Chalcolithic ceramics from Cyprus[☆]

Maria Hadjigavriel^{a,*} , Maria Dikomitou Eliadou^b

^a Leiden University, Netherlands

^b The Cyprus Institute, Cyprus

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Ceramic petrography
Ceramic technology
handheld XRF
Late Chalcolithic
Pottery studies
Prehistoric Cyprus
Regional pottery traditions

ABSTRACT

The Late Chalcolithic period (ca. 2900–2400 BCE) in Cyprus represents a dynamic phase characterised by significant societal and material transformations, laying the foundation for the island's transition into the Bronze Age. In pottery production, notable developments include a focus on red and/or black monochrome wares, which were produced across the island. This paper presents findings of an intra- and inter-site compositional and technological analysis of ceramic fabrics from four Late Chalcolithic sites in southwestern and central Cyprus, i. e., Chlorakas-Palloures, Kissonerga-Mosphilia, Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, and Politiko-Kokkinorotsos. The study examines Red and Black Stroke-Burnished, Red Monochrome, and Spalled Wares, and samples of Red (and Black) Lustrous and Coarse wares. These ceramics were analysed using ceramic thin section petrography and handheld energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry to determine their mineralogical, chemical, and technological characteristics. The analytical data have been integrated with contextual information and a prior detailed macroscopic examination of the selected samples. This project aims to investigate pottery technologies and assess the degree of fabric variability at local, regional, and inter-regional levels. Additionally, it explores pottery production processes and pottery distribution patterns, with a particular focus on identifying potential inter-site interaction within Cyprus during the Late Chalcolithic period.

1. Introducing Late Chalcolithic ceramic culture

In contrast to the Middle Chalcolithic period, when patterned-painted decoration, as exemplified by Red-on-White ware, dominates the island's ceramic repertoire (Bolger and Webb, 2013: 44), the Late Chalcolithic period marks a shift towards the production of monochrome wares. These include a variety of red and/or black monochrome types, such as Red/Black Stroke Burnished, Spalled ware, Red Lustrous and Red-Black Lustrous ware, and Coarse Painted ware (monochrome), among others. These wares were locally produced at each site, across the island and are characterised by red-slipped and burnished surfaces and/or blackened surfaces, occasionally featuring relief decoration (Peltenburg, 1991; Bolger, 2013; Bolger and Webb, 2013).

The Late Chalcolithic monochrome wares encompass various forms, classified based on fabric, shape, and decorative techniques, and are described using a diverse range of terms (see Table 3.1 in Bolger and Webb, 2013: 47). The complex terminology associated with these

ceramics reflects the challenges in the stratigraphic and typological correlation of ceramic assemblages from different regions of Cyprus. This difficulty arises from the scarcity of stratified archaeological material outside the island's southwestern region (Bolger and Webb, 2013: 47). Different ware groups from various sites correlate primarily in terms of surface treatment and general shape repertoire, as they are mostly red monochrome with red/black burnished surfaces, typically found in bowls and jars.

The challenge in terminology and inter-site chronological correlation is indeed significant and warrants thorough examination. Careful sampling of diagnostic fragments—prioritising those with distinct shape or fabric characteristics over body sherds—becomes crucial in making meaningful inter-site comparisons. Fabric, as understood macroscopically, serves also as a distinguishing feature between groups, allowing us to establish technological variability (or similarities) across sites. Moreover, stratigraphic and chronological differences between the chosen sites influence both the selection of samples and the

[☆] This paper is part of the VSI 'Proceedings of ICAS-EMME 4', edited by M. Desai et al. (2025). This article is part of a special issue entitled: 'Proceedings of ICAS-EMME 4' published in Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports.

* Corresponding author at: Einsteinweg 2, 2333CC Leiden, Netherlands.

E-mail address: m.hadjigavriel@arch.leidenuniv.nl (M. Hadjigavriel).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2025.105143>

Received 2 December 2024; Received in revised form 27 March 2025; Accepted 7 April 2025

Available online 2 May 2025

2352-409X/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

interpretation of data. These differences necessitate a nuanced approach, where the relationship between ceramic traditions is carefully considered in light of regional and chronological contexts.

The aim of profiling different regional ceramic traditions with a primary focus on ceramic fabric analysis, is to clarify technological distinctions while also enabling inter-site comparative studies. This broader approach helps overcome limitations of terminology and provides a more comprehensive understanding of ceramic wares and technological differences between the sites.

In southwestern Cyprus, the predominant ware is Red Black Stroke-Burnished Ware (hereafter RB/B), which has been found in Late Chalcolithic contexts at sites such as Lemba-Lakkous, Kissonerga-Mosphilia and Chlorakas-Palloures (Stewart, 1985; Bolger et al., 1998; Hadjigavriel, 2019; 2021). RB/B ware is characterised by light red, pink or orange colours, highly burnished surfaces often bearing stroke marks, blackened areas, and occasional relief decoration. It predominantly appears in bowls (sometimes spouted), jars, platters, flasks, and bottles (Bolger and Webb, 2013). Previous studies suggest experimentation with clay and slip, and a shift towards more standardised production methods (e.g. Wallace, 1995).

In the northwestern part of the island, Red Lustrous Ware (hereafter RL) and Red Black Lustrous Ware (hereafter RBL) dominate Late Chalcolithic pottery production at sites such as Ambelikou-Agios Georgios (Dikaïos, 1962; Paraskeva, 2017). These wares share characteristics with RB/B Ware, including red and/or black burnished surfaces and occasional relief decoration (Dikaïos, 1962; Bolger and Webb, 2013). A similar ware has also been identified at Politiko-Kokkinorotsos, in central Cyprus. At Politiko, unpainted monochrome pottery was not

categorised based on surface colour (e.g., monochrome red or monochrome black). Instead, since the pottery exhibits overlapping attributes and appears to belong to a single ceramic production tradition, the excavators chose to interpret it as “varieties or extremes within a broad range rather than as separate ‘wares’”. Consequently, the pottery was classified into fabric varieties A to E within the unpainted tradition (Webb et al., 2009: 196).

This paper presents the results of an intra- and inter-site compositional and technological assessment of ceramic fabrics from four contemporary Late Chalcolithic sites in south-western, north-western, and central Cyprus. The selected sites are Chlorakas-Palloures and Kissonerga-Mosphilia in the southwest, Ambelikou-Agios Georgios in the northwest, and Politiko-Kokkinorotsos in central Cyprus (Fig. 1). The latter two sites are located in the northwestern and northeastern foothills of the Troodos Mountain range, respectively.

This study aims to delineate the regional characteristics of ceramic production as reflected in the fabrics from these sites and their respective regions. Additionally, it investigates pottery-making choices, their degree of technological variability at a local, regional and inter-regional level, ceramic distribution, as well as the possible identification of inter-site interactive networks during the Late Chalcolithic period.

2. Research objectives, sample selection, and analytical methodology

Ceramic tradition encompasses the transmission and continuity of cultural practices, skills, and knowledge over time (Darvill 2008, 466–467; Hobsbawm and Ranger 1983), shaping both tangible and

Fig. 1. Map indicating the location of the sites selected for this study (digital data of the Cyprus Geological Survey Department).

intangible heritage. In ceramic studies, the term tradition is expressed through materials, techniques, and styles, which together reflect both cultural identity and technological continuity (Roux 2016; 2019; 2020). A key component of every tradition, and the focus of this study, is ceramic fabric (Santacreu 2014), i.e., the material composition of fired clay, including its texture, composition, and structure (Whitbread 1995: 368).

Fabric influences the artefact's strength, porosity, and durability, making it integral to both functionality and aesthetics (Dikomitou and Georgiou, 2024, and references therein; Sillar and Tite 2000; Rice 2015; Santacreu 2017). Variations in fabric, such as different clay types and tempering agents, could serve as technological and/or cultural markers that distinguish ceramic traditions across regions and historical periods (Dobres 1999; 2010; Santacreu 2017). Fabric analysis provides valuable insight into understanding aspects of these traditions, particularly as ceramic fabric relates to the geological context and geographic location of pottery-making communities (Arnold 2000). The variability in fabric composition is influenced by the availability of raw materials but also the methods used by potters to select and process them (Arnold 2000). This reinforces the idea that fabric, or paste composition, can be a distinguishing feature of consistent, long-term technological practices. In geological regions with limited changes in raw material resources, the persistence of certain fabric characteristics over time further underscores the continuity of these traditions, reflecting both the potters' reliance on local material sources and their adaptation to the environment.

The compositional and technological study of ceramic fabrics provides valuable insights into raw material sources, production techniques, and cultural connections. This study considers ceramic fabric within a broader regional framework, with the sampled sites serving as representatives of the geological regions to which they belong, reflecting the material properties and production practices characteristic of each area. By characterising the technological and compositional aspects of Late Chalcolithic pottery, this research contributes to understanding regional ceramic traditions and their broader historical significance.

This study takes into account the different types of sites, the topographical differences among them (Fig. 1), and the approaches used in their investigation. Chlorakas-Palloures and Kissonerga-Mosphilia are two large coastal settlements. The former is currently under excavation (Düring et al. 2019, 2021), while the latter was excavated in the 1980s by the Lemba Archaeological Project and has been extensively published (Peltenburg, 1998; 2000; 2003).

Conversely, the other two sites, Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and Politiko-Kokkinorotsos, are inland sites located at the northern foothills of the Troodos Mountain range. Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, situated in the northwestern occupied part of Cyprus, was investigated via two trial trenches excavated by Dikaos in the 1930s and 1940s, revealing a single building (Dikaos, 1962). The pottery from this site was later re-examined by Gjerstad and Peltenburg in the 1980s (Dikaos, 1962; Gjerstad, 1980; Peltenburg, 1991). Lastly, Politiko-Kokkinorotsos was excavated by Frankel and Webb in the early 2000s and is interpreted as a seasonal hunting station (Webb et al., 2009).

The diverse site types included in this study enabled the assessment of variability of ceramic fabrics within distinct socioeconomic and regional settings. This comparative approach aimed to enhance our understanding of the technological and compositional similarities or differences in pottery production, providing insights into regional ceramic traditions and artefact circulation.

This study focused on representative wares from Late Chalcolithic sites, primarily those identified as locally produced based on typological and stylistic criteria. A few exceptions, which are vessels likely produced elsewhere, were included to examine the scale of ceramic distribution. Specifically, the study investigates the hypothesis that pottery produced in western Cyprus has been found in the north-central regions and vice versa.

The sampled wares include RB/B, RL, and RBL. These wares were

predominant in Late Chalcolithic contexts, forming the bulk of pottery production at each site (Dikaos, 1962; Bolger et al., 1998; Webb et al., 2009; Bolger and Webb, 2013; Hadjigavriel, 2021). They are comparable due to their monochrome red and/or black, highly burnished surfaces, fine and hard fabrics, occasional relief decoration, and their predominance in bowls and storage jars (Bolger and Webb, 2013; Hadjigavriel, 2019; 2021). In addition to these, three more wares have been selected, as outlined below.

Spalled Ware (hereafter SW) is a prominent Late Chalcolithic ware (Bolger and Webb, 2013). It is characterised by its extreme hardness and the presence of white inclusions visible macroscopically on both the sherd surface and in cross-section (Bolger et al., 1998; Bolger and Webb, 2013).

Additionally, Late Chalcolithic Red Monochrome Ware samples (hereafter LChalRM) were selected exclusively from Chlorakas-Palloures due to the ware's high occurrence in storage jars and its significance as one of the site's primary Late Chalcolithic wares. It accounts for about 15% of the Late Chalcolithic pottery retrieved at Chlorakas-Palloures, in contrast to the RB/B and the SW, which account for the remaining 85%. This, along with the ware's fabric, as understood from macroscopic observations, suggests non-local production.

Finally, Coarse Ware (hereafter CW) has been sampled from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and Politiko-Kokkinorotsos. Coarse Ware is a low-fired, utilitarian ware with little to no surface treatment, typically associated with domestic contexts. It occurs in flat-based pans or trays and is common across Middle and Late Chalcolithic sites. It is thought to have been produced locally, and its selection aims to cross-check whether the same local fabrics were used for different ceramic types within the wide spectrum of pottery production (Webb et al., 2009: 196; Bolger and Webb, 2013). All these wares represent the predominant Late Chalcolithic pottery production at the selected sites. They are as contemporaneous as possible, given the available material, and comparable in terms of surface treatment and vessel shapes (Fig. 2; Table 1).

Following a macroscopic overview of the site assemblages, 81 sherds were selected for further study (Table 2). These samples represent the most characteristic wares and vessel shapes from each site (Dikomitou Eliadou and Kiriati, 2023). Given the coarseness of the clay paste in the selected samples and, more generally, in Cypriot Late Chalcolithic pottery, ceramic petrography was deemed the most suitable method for material characterisation. In the laboratory, ceramic thin sections, 30 µm thick, were prepared from all samples following the standard procedure for petrographic analysis. The thin sections were then examined under a polarising microscope using transmitted polarised light (ZEISS AxioLab 5) at magnifications ranging between 25x and 400x, using Plain Polarised Light (PPL) and Crossed Polarised Light (XPL). The recording system used here is an adjusted version of the system established by Whitbread (1995).

Additionally, this study used handheld energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence (hhXRF) spectrometry to test the correspondence between the petrographic and elemental groupings, aiming to assess whether compositional variations observed in thin section align with chemical differences, thereby strengthening the reliability of the petrographic classification and interpretation of the ceramic assemblage. HhXRF analysers have become popular in material studies for their versatile, in-situ application, enabling non-invasive, rapid, and cost-effective chemical characterisation of archaeological materials (Foster et al., 2011; Frahm and Doonan, 2013; Tykot, 2016).

3. The macroscopic examination of the selected samples

The macroscopic examination of the selected ceramic fabrics was conducted using a 10x magnification hand lens and a 400x USB microscope (Veho Discovery VMS004). Macroscopic descriptions followed the guidelines provided by Orton et al. (2003: 67–75, 231–242). All fragments were classified as hard (between 3 and 4 on the Mohs hardness scale), with the exception of six CW samples which were identified

Fig. 2. Representative samples of the wares included in this study and examples of popular vessel shapes in Late Chalcolithic Cyprus (created by Maria Hadjigavriel and Ermina Emmanuel after Bolger & Webb, 2013).

Table 1
Overview of the wares included in this study (by Maria Hadjigavriel).

	Red Black Stroked-Burnished Ware (RB/B)	Late Chalcolithic Red Monochrome Ware (LChalRM)	Red Lustrous Ware (RL)	Red Black Lustrous Ware (RBL)	Spalled Ware (SW)	Coarse Ware (CW)
Surface Treatment						
Red – highly burnished/lustre	X	X	X			
Red – highly burnished/lustre with irregular blackened surfaces	X	X	X			
Red – highly burnished/lustre and regularly blackened surfaces				X		
Grey – brown slip					X	
Relief decoration	X		X	X		
Untreated						X
Fabric						
Soft						X
Hard	X	X	X	X		
Very hard					X	
Popular Shapes						
Bowls > jars	X			X		
Jars < bowls		X	X		X	
Trays						X

as soft (2 on the Mohs hardness scale). Overall, six macrofabrics were identified and are presented in Table 3 and Fig. 3.

These six macrofabrics (Table 3, Fig. 3) are characterised by differences in matrix colour, inclusions, reduction patterns, and hardness. Macrofabric Group 1 exhibits a vibrant pink to orange matrix (e.g., 5YR 5/6, 2.5YR 5/6) with inclusions in bluish-grey and red tones. The clay matches the surface colour, and the fragments are uniformly through-fired or show sharp core margins, suggesting a reduction phase during firing or unintentional oxidation prevention. Inclusion frequency ranges from 20%–30%, with poorly sorted inclusions typically measuring 0.5–3.0 mm in size. All fragments in this group are hard, ranking

between gypsum and calcite on the Mohs scale. This macrofabric corresponds exclusively to the RB/B and is primarily associated with Chlorakas-Palloures and Kissonerga-Mosphilia, with a few examples recorded in Ambelikou-Agios Georgios.

Macrofabric Group 2 is defined by pink-buff clays (e.g., 7.5YR 4/1, 2.5YR 5/4) and a dark inner core. The inclusions are similar to Macrofabric Group 1 but include larger white particles. Inclusion frequency is 20 %, with inclusions poorly sorted and measuring 0.5–3.0 mm. The fragments are very hard, reflecting the dense and compact nature of the fabric. This macrofabric corresponds exclusively to the SW and is primarily found in Chlorakas-Palloures and Kissonerga-Mosphilia, with

Table 2

The 81 samples included in this study (by Maria Hadjigavriel).

Sample Code	Ware	Site of recovery	Context	Shape
S1	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	86	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S2	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	115	jar – straight constant rounded rim
S3	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	E1	hole-mouth jar – slightly flaring thinning rounded rim
S4	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	118	jar – straight thinning pointed rim
S5	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	174	jar with spout – flaring constant rounded rim
S6	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	10	hole-mouth jar – flaring thinning rounded rim
S7	RL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	10	hole-mouth jar – straight constant rounded rim
S8	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	37	hole-mouth jar – straight thinning rounded rim
S9	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	198	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S10	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	53	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S11	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	71	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S12	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	198	jar with spout – straight thinning rounded rim
S13	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	125	jar – flaring constant rounded rim
S14	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	113	jar – straight constant rounded rim
S15	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	B1	jar – straight thinning rounded rim
S16	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	198	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S17	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	62	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S18	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	198	jar – straight constant rounded rim
S19	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	11	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S20	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	198	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S21	RBL	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	198	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S22	CW	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	2	pan/tray – base
S23	CW	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	71	pan/tray – base

Table 2 (continued)

Sample Code	Ware	Site of recovery	Context	Shape
S24	CW	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	67	pan/tray – base
S25	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 3-Lot 1641	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S26	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BU13-Unit 34-Lot 1413	bowl – flaring constant rounded rim
S27	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 3-Lot 1596	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S28	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BQ09-Unit 31-Lot 851	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S29	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 3-Lot 1641	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S30	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BX14-Unit 4-Lot 210	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S31	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 15-Lot 1726	bowl – flaring thinning pointed rim
S32	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BT13-Unit12-Lot 1772	bowl – slightly flaring thinning pointed rim
S33	RB/B	Chlorakas-Palloures	BT13-Unit 11-Lot 1976	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S34	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BT13-Unit 11-Lot 1960	jar – closed body sherd
S35	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 3-Lot 1641	bowl – flaring constant rounded rim
S36	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 3-Lot 1641	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S37	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BO19-Unit 6-Lot 1665	bowl – flaring thinning rounded rim
S38	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 3-Lot 1637	jar – straight constant rounded rim
S39	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BI21-Unit 9-Lot 2034	jar – closed body sherd

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Sample Code	Ware	Site of recovery	Context	Shape
S40	SW	Chlorakas-Palloures	BT13-Unit 5-Lot 1781	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
		Chlorakas-Palloures	Building 18	
S41	LChalRM	Chlorakas-Palloures	BU12-Unit 14-Lot 572	jar – closed body sherd
		Chlorakas-Palloures	Building 5	
S42	LChalRM	Chlorakas-Palloures	BO19-Unit 2-Lot 1448	jar – flaring thinning rounded rim
		Chlorakas-Palloures	Building X	
S43	LChalRM	Chlorakas-Palloures	BR10-Unit 9-Lot 510	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
		Chlorakas-Palloures	Building 4	
S44	LChalRM	Chlorakas-Palloures	BT13-Unit 19-Lot 1996	jar – open body sherd
		Chlorakas-Palloures	Building 18	
S45	LChalRM	Chlorakas-Palloures	BT13-Unit 14-Lot 1786	jar – flaring thinning rounded rim
		Chlorakas-Palloures	Building 18	
S46	RB/B	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1175	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, fill associated with structure 1052	
S47	RB/B	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1138	bowl – open body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, fill associated with structure 834	
S48	RB/B	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 471	bowl – open body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, pit associated with structure 706	
S49	RB/B	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 471	bowl – open body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, pit associated with structure 706	
S50	RB/B	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1044	bowl – open body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, building structure 1044	
S51	SW	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1339	bowl – open body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, associated with structure 1165	
S52	RB/B	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1044	jar – closed body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, building structure 1044	
S53	SW	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1162	jar – closed body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit pot spread associated with structure 1052	
S54	SW	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1044	jar – closed body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit, building structure 1044	

Table 2 (continued)

Sample Code	Ware	Site of recovery	Context	Shape
S55	SW	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1162	jar – closed body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit pot spread associated with structure 1052	
S56	SW	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	KM 1162	jar – closed body sherd
		Kissonerga-Mosphilia	in situ deposit pot spread associated with structure 1052	
S57	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 194A	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S58	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 192A	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S59	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 185	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S60	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 187	jar – constant flaring rounded rim
S61	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 174	bowl – constant flaring rounded rim
S62	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 172	bowl – open body sherd
S63	RL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 175	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S64	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 184	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S65	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 187	bowl – open body sherd
S66	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 171 – 162	bowl – flaring thinning pointed rim
S67	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 183	bowl – open body sherd
S68	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 172	bowl – slightly flaring thinning rounded rim
S69	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 184	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S70	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 194A	bowl – straight thinning rounded rim
S71	RBL	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 171 – 169	bowl – straight thinning pointed rim
S72	RB/B	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 171 – 165	bowl – straight constant pointed rim
S73	RB/B	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 195	bowl – straight constant rounded rim
S74	SW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 171	jar – closed body sherd
S75	SW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 171	jar – closed body sherd
S76	SW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 173	jar – closed body sherd
S77	SW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 170	jar – closed body sherd
S78	SW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 170	Spout
S79	CW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 176	pan/tray – base
S80	CW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 177	pan/tray – base
S81	CW	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Tray 176	pan/tray – base

Table 3
Overview of the macrofabric groups identified in this study (by Maria Hadjigavriel).

Macrofabric group no.	Wares	Sites	Hardness	Reduction – Core	Matrix Colour	Incl. colour	Incl. frequency	Incl. sorting	Incl. size	
1	RB/B	●Chlorakas-Palloures ●Kissonerga-Mosphilia ●Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Hard	Reduced, diffused core margins	5YR 4/2	Beige Brown Grey Red	20 %-30 %	Poor	0.5–3.0 mm	
				or	2.5YR 5/6	Blue White				
				Reduced, no core	2.5Y 5/2					
					5YR 5/6 2.5YR 5/6 5YR 6/4					
2	SW	●Chlorakas-Palloures ●Kissonerga-Mosphilia ●Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Very hard	Reduced, diffused core margins	7.5YR 4/1	Grey Orange Red Blue White	20 %	Poor	0.5–3.0 mm	
				or	2.5Y 5.1					
				Reduced, no core	7.5YR 3/2					
					7.5R 5/3 2.5YR 5/4 5Y 5/1 5YR 6/3					
3	LChalRM	●Chlorakas-Palloures	Hard	Reduced, diffused core margins	7.5YR 5/2 7.5YR 5/3 5YR 5/4 10YR 4/3	Grey, Brown Orange White	20 %	Poor	0.5–2.0 mm	
					7.5YR 5/3					
4	RBL	●Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	Hard	Reduced, diffused core margins	7.5YR 5/3	Beige Brown Grey	10 %-20 %	Poor	0.5–1.0 mm	
	RL			or Reduced, no core	7.5YR 5/4 2.5YR 5/6 7.5YR 5/2 5YR 5/4 2.5YR 4/4 7.5YR 5/3	Red Orange White				
5	RBL	●Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	Hard	Reduced, diffused core margins	2.5YR 4/4	Beige Brown Grey Orange Grey White	20 %-30 %	Poor	0.5–1.0 mm	
	RL			or Reduced, no core	5YR 5/4 2.5YR 5/4 2.5YR 4/4 10R 5/6 2.5Y 5/2					
6	CW	●Chlorakas-Palloures ●Kissonerga-Mosphilia ●Ambelikou-Agios Georghios ●Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	Very soft	Oxidised, no core	7.5YR 5/2	Grey Brown Orange White	20 %	Poor	0.5–2.0 mm	
						7.5YR 5/3				
						5YR 5/4				
						10YR 4/3				

occasional examples from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios.

Macrofabric Group 3 features dark brown clay (e.g., 7.5YR 5/2, 5YR 5/4) with a distinctive blackened biscuit core. It contains white inclusions and elongated voids, indicative of burned organic temper. Sparse angular grey igneous temper is also present. Inclusions are poorly sorted, with a frequency of $\leq 20\%$, and their size ranges from 0.5–1.0 mm. All fragments are hard. This macrofabric corresponds to the LChalRM, exclusively from Chlorakas-Palloures.

Macrofabric Group 4 sherds exhibit yellowish-red or brown clays (e.g., 7.5YR 4/3, 2.5YR 4/4), always in a reduced state, occasionally with a diffused core. Inclusions vary in colour (beige to white) and size (0.5–1.0 mm), with a frequency of $\leq 20\%$. Petrographic studies identified some inclusions as limestone fragments. All ceramic sherds are hard (3 on the Mohs scale). This macrofabric is found exclusively at Politiko-Kokkinorotsos and corresponds to the RL and the RBL, matching Webb's Fabric A, B, and D.

Macrofabric Group 5 features light brown to red clay with beige, brown, grey, orange, and white inclusions. Sections typically have a central core with diffused or sharp margins, reflecting a reduction phase during firing. Inclusion size ranges from 0.5–1.0 mm, with a frequency of $\leq 20\%$. Sorting is poor and fragments are hard (3–4 on the Mohs scale). This group is exclusively found at Ambelikou-Agios Georghios

and corresponds to the RL and the RBL.

Macrofabric Group 6 is the coarsest within the selected sample, and displays light to dark brown clay with large grey, white, and sometimes organic inclusions. Inclusion size ranges from 0.5–2.0 mm, with a frequency of $\leq 20\%$, and sorting is poor. All fragments are very soft (2 on the Mohs scale). This macrofabric is present across all four sites and corresponds to Coarse Ware (CW). The coarseness of the clay, the big inclusions and the low firing temperatures that do not result to colour changes are consistent features across all samples attributed to this Macrofabric Group. Additionally, even though Coarse Ware is present at all for sites, for this project, it has only been sampled from Politiko-Kokkinorotsos and Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, where the pottery repertoires have close parallels (Webb et al., 2009).

The macroscopic analysis has shown both similarities and differences between regional pottery productions and pottery-making decisions. In Chlorakas-Palloures and Kissonerga-Mosphilia, the RB/B (Macrofabric Group 1) and the SW (Macrofabric Group 2) are clearly comparable. They share similarities in forming techniques (pinching and coiling), macroscopic fabric, and firing regime (high temperatures, reduced firing conditions) as reflected in fabric hardness and the appearance of firing cores in cross section. However, the dominant presence of white inclusions (later identified as limestone by petrographic examination) and

Fig. 3. Examples of the Macrofabric Groups identified in this study (low magnification microphotographs, scale bar size: 2 mm).

the hardness of SW distinguishes them from the RB/B samples in Macrofabric Group 1. Additionally, their surface treatment is different, with the RB/B being self-slipped and highly burnished, while the SW is covered with a dull beige to grey slip, and while the RB/B occurs mainly in bowls, the SW occurs mainly in closed vessel shapes such as jugs and jars. The LChalRM (Macrofabric Group 3) represents a separate technological practice at Chlorakas-Palloures. It occurs almost exclusively in large storage jars, the exterior surface is covered with a red slip while the interior remains untreated, and the cross section is of brown colours, dominated by a large dark core.

The RL and RBL from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and Politiko-Kokkinorotsos differ in macrofabric, corresponding to Macrofabric Group 4 and Macrofabric Group 5, respectively. Despite this, they share common technological traits, including vessel surface treatments (e.g. red medium-burnished surfaces), forming techniques (coiling, and pinch and draw forming), and firing techniques (homogenous blackened surfaces and occasionally black rims). Finally, the CW (Macrofabric Group 6) is sampled from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and Politiko-Kokkinorotsos, and shows consistency in production techniques, despite its coarse nature.

4. The petrographic examination of Late Chalcolithic pottery

Ceramic petrography was employed to characterise the mineralogical composition of the samples as well as technological features that could identify local pottery productions and indicate distinct regional ceramic traditions and the provenance of the vessels.

The classification of the samples into petrographic fabric groups and the documentation of visible technological features provided the foundation for the identification of regional pottery making traditions, as well as assessing inter-site technological and compositional variability. Additionally, this analysis facilitated the identification of imported

pottery and its significance for understanding ceramic circulation, offering insights into interactions between communities.

The results were integrated with macroscopic observations, allowing for a more concrete assessment of the established typological classification of pottery wares, supported by evidence regarding the production technology of the wares under study. The 81 ceramic samples were grouped into seven distinct fabrics, while four samples remained outliers, as shown in Table 4. Detailed descriptions of the fabric groups are provided in Tables 5 and 6.

4.1. Fabric I: Fabric with dominant presence of argillaceous inclusions

Fabric I is represented by nine samples. Six were recovered from Chlorakas-Palloures, one from Kissonerga-Mosphilia, and two from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, all associated with RB/B ware. This fabric is characterised by a dominant presence of argillaceous inclusions, alongside chert and sandstone. The term “argillaceous inclusions” follows Whitbread (1986) and refers to clay-rich materials, typically indicative of a predominantly clay-based rock composition.

The inclusions display variability in composition and textural characteristics, even within the same thin section. Most are identified as mudstone fragments, typically grey in colour, with some containing unidentified constituents in very fine fraction. Partial oxidation is evident in some fragments, leading to colour transitions to brown or reddish-brown, while others range from dark yellow to dark reddish-brown. These colour variations are attributed to factors such as composition (e.g., iron oxide content, water content, organic matter) and firing conditions (temperature, atmosphere, duration).

Other inclusions in Fabric I include monocrystalline quartz, chert, and opaques. Occasionally, sandstone fragments containing quartz, iron oxides, opaque minerals, and/or mica, as well as small feldspar laths, are observed. Rarely textural concentration features are also noted, such as

Table 4

The identified ceramic fabrics as defined by ceramic thin section petrography (by Maria Hadjigavriel).

Fabric no.	Short fabric description	No. of samples	% of samples	Samples	Wares	Macrofabric Group	Site(s) represented
I	Fabric with dominant presence of argillaceous inclusions	9	11 %	S25, S28, S29, S30, S31, S32, S47, S72, S73	RB/B	1	– Palloures (6 samples) – Mosphilia (1 sample) – Ambelikou (2 samples)
II	Fabric with dominant presence of argillaceous inclusions, common sandstone and few dolerite fragments	7	9 %	S26, S27, S33, S46, S48, S50, S52	RB/B	1	• Palloures (3 samples) • Mosphilia (4 samples)
III	Fabric with dominant presence of micritic limestone and chert	17	21 %	S34, S35, S36, S37, S38, S39, S40, S51, S53, S54, S55, S56, S74, S75, S76, S77, S78	SW	2	• Palloures (7 samples) • Mosphilia (5 samples) • Ambelikou (5 samples)
IV	Fabric with dominant presence of amphibole, feldspars and quartz	5	6 %	S41, S42, S43, S44, S45	LChalRM	3	• Palloures (5 samples)
V	Fabric with dominant presence of carbonates	10	12 %	S4, S8, S11, S14, S15, S18, S19, S20, S21	RL, RBL	4	• Politiko (10 samples)
VI	Fabric with dominant presence of feldspars and dolerite	14	17 %	S1, S2, S3, S5, S6, S7, S9, S12, S10, S13, S16, S17, S22, S23, S24	RL, RBL, CW	4 6	• Politiko (14 samples)
VII	Fabric with dominant presence of dolerite and basalt	15	19 %	S57, S58, S59, S60, S61, S62, S63, S64, S65, S66, S67, S68, S69, S70, S81	RL, RBL, CW	5 6	• Ambelikou (15 samples)
Outlier 1	Fabric with dominant presence of red argillaceous inclusions	1	1.25 %	S49	RB/B	1	• Mosphilia (1 sample)
Outlier 2	Fabric with dominant presence of igneous inclusions and chert	1	1.25 %	S71	RBL	5	• Ambelikou (1 sample)
Outlier 3	Fabric with dominant presence of quartz, basalt and clinopyroxenes	1	1.25 %	S79	CW	6	• Ambelikou (1 sample)
Outlier 4	Fabric with dominant presence of chert and orthopyroxenes	1	1.25 %	S80	CW	6	• Ambelikou (1 sample)
Totals		81	100				

Table 5

Description of the seven main petrographic fabrics of this study (++ = dominant; +=common; - = few; -- = rare; by Maria Hadjigavriel).

Petrographic	Fabric	Fabric	Fabric	Fabric	Fabric	Fabric	Fabric
fabric	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Sample (n =)	9 (11 %)	7 (9 %)	17 (21 %)	5 (6 %)	10 (12 %)	14 (17 %)	15 (18 %)
(% of the overall sample)							
Sample codes	S25, S28, S29, S30, S31, S32, S47, S72, S73	S26, S27, S33, S46, S48, S50, S52	S34, 35, S36, S37, S38, S39, S40, S51, S53, S54, S55, S56, S74, S75, S76, S77, S78	S41, S42, S43, S44, S45	S4, S8, S11, S14, S15, S16, S18, S19, S20, S21	S1,S2, S3, S5, S6, S7, S9, S12, S10, S13, S17, S22, S23, S24	S57, S58, S59, S60, S61, S62, S63, S64, S65, S66, S67, S68, S69, S70, S81
Matrix (XP)	light to dark orange; moderately optically active to optically inactive	dark orange to dark brown; moderately optically active	dark yellow/orange to dark brown; moderately optically active	yellow to dark orange and dark brown/grey; moderately optically active	dark orange/red to dark grey/brown; moderately optically active	yellow to red/orange, and dark grey/brown; moderately optically active	dark orange/red to dark grey/brown; moderately optically active
Voids	rare meso planar voids parallel to the section's margins (<2%); rare macro vughs (<5%); dominant meso and micro vughs (<10%); randomly oriented; close- to double-spaced	some mega planar voids parallel or vertical to the section's margins (<5%); frequent meso and micro vughs (<10%); randomly oriented; close- to double-spaced	common to few planar voids, parallel to the section's margins (<5%); rare meso vughs (<2%); dominant micro vughs (<10%); randomly oriented; close- to double-spaced	common to few planar voids parallel to the section's margins (<10%); rare meso vughs (<2%); common micro vughs (<5%); randomly oriented; close- to double-spaced	rare to absent planar voids (<2%); rare macro vughs (<5%); common meso and micro-vughs (<10%); randomly oriented; single to open-spaced	rare to absent planar voids (<2%); rare macro vughs (<2%); common meso and micro-vughs (<5%); randomly oriented; single to open-spaced	rare to absent planar voids (<1%); rare macro vughs (<2%); common meso and micro-vughs (<5%); randomly oriented; single to open-spaced
Grain size							
–coarse fraction	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand
–fine fraction	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below
c:f:v 0.0625 mm	45:45:10	50:45:05	50:45:05	55:35:10	45:45:10	55:40:05	45:45:10
Inclusions	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant argillaceous inclusions (++); common chert & opaques (+); few monocrystalline quartz (-); rare sandstone, textural concentration features & feldspars (--)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant argillaceous inclusions, chert & serpentinite (++); common sandstone, polycrystalline quartz & opaques (+); few siltstone, gabbro, basalt & micritic limestone (-)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant micritic limestone, chert & argillaceous inclusions (++); common sandstone, polycrystalline quartz, opaques & serpentinite (+); few polycrystalline quartz, basalt and calcite (-)	well sorted inclusions; bimodal grain distribution; dominant amphiboles, monocrystalline & polycrystalline quartz (++); common serpentinite, basalt, olivine, dolerite (+); few gabbro, sandstone, quartzite, opaques & micritic limestone (-)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain distribution; dominant microfossils, micritic limestone & feldspars (++); common serpentinite, opaques, basalt, polycrystalline quartz (+); few sandstone & dolerite (-); rare olivine, orthopyroxenes & clinopyroxenes (-)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain distribution; dominant feldspar, polycrystalline quartz & dolerite (++); common serpentinite, biotite, monocrystalline quartz, opaques, clay pellets & orthopyroxenes (+), few basalt & clinopyroxenes (-); rare olivine, sandstone, micritic limestone & microfossils (--)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain distribution; dominant dolerite & basalt (++); common clinopyroxenes, feldspar, monocrystalline & polycrystalline quartz & opaques (+); few amphiboles & olivine (-); rare granitic rock
% (sub) rounded – % (sub) angular	60–40	50–50	50–50	40–60	30–70	60–40	60–40

in sample S25, which contains an argillaceous matrix, quartz, and small sedimentary rock fragments with a micritic texture and darker brown fabric. The lack of significant clay refinement is evidenced by the coarse size of the inclusions, which reach the size of pebbles. Variations in the optical activity of the samples—from active to completely inactive or blackened—suggest firing temperature and atmospheric differences within this fabric group (Fig. 4).

4.2. Fabric II: Fabric with dominant argillaceous inclusions, common sandstone and few dolerite fragments

Fabric II comprises of seven samples, characterised by argillaceous inclusions, sandstone and dolerite fragments. These samples, derived from Chlorakas-Palloures and Kissonerga-Mosphilia, and they belong to

RB/B ware. Similar to Fabric I, the matrix features argillaceous inclusions of varying hues (grey, yellow, and red), chert, and serpentinite. Additional inclusions include polycrystalline quartz, opaques, and siltstone.

While comparable to Fabric I, Fabric II appears to originate from a distinct clay source, indicated by a higher degree of inclusion mixing and a more heterogeneous matrix. The presence of red/orange serpentinite inclusions suggests firing temperatures exceeded 650°C, as serpentinite undergoes colour changes between 650°C and 750°C (Vitti, 2010; Travé Allepuz, 2021) (Fig. 5).

Table 6

Description of the four outliers of this study (++ = dominant; +=common; - = few; -- = rare; by Maria Hadjigavriel).

Petrographic fabric	Outlier 1: Fabric with dominant presence of red argillaceous inclusions	Outlier 2: Fabric with dominant presence of igneous inclusions & chert	Outlier 3: Fabric with dominant presence of quartz, basalts & clinopyroxenes	Outlier 4: Fabric with dominant presence of radiolarian chert & orthopyroxenes
Sample (n =) (% of the overall sample)	1 (1 %)	1 (1 %)	1 (1 %)	1 (1 %)
Sample codes	S49	S71	S79	S80
Matrix (XP)	light to dark orange; moderately optically active	dark orange/red to dark grey/brown; moderately optically active	dark orange/red to dark grey/brown; moderately optically active	dark orange/red to dark grey/brown; moderately optically active
Voids	dominant meso & micro vughs (<10 %); some meso planar voids, occasionally parallel to the section's margins (<5%); rare macro vughs (<2%); randomly oriented; close- to double-spaced	rare to absent planar voids (<1%); rare macro vughs (<2%) and common meso & micro-vughs (<5%); randomly oriented; single to open-spaced	rare to absent planar voids (<1%); rare macro vughs (<2%); common meso & micro-vughs (<5%); randomly oriented; single to open-spaced	rare to absent planar voids (<1%); rare macro vughs (<2%); common meso & micro-vughs (<5%); randomly oriented; single to open-spaced
Grain size				
–coarse fraction	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand	–from pebbles to fine sand
–fine fraction	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below	–of fine sand & below
c:f:v 0.0625 mm	60:35:05	45:45:10	45:45:10	65:25:10
Inclusions	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant red/brown argillaceous inclusions (++); common chert & opaques (+); few quartz (-); rare sandstone (-)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant dolerite & radiolarian chert (++); common feldspars, sandstone, opaques & quartz (+); few olivine (-)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant quartz, basalt & clinopyroxenes (++); common feldspar, dolerite & opaques (+); few olivine (-)	poorly sorted inclusions; bimodal grain-size distribution; dominant radiolarian chert, orthopyroxenes & micritic limestone (++); common quartz & opaques (+); few olivine (-)
% (sub)rounded	60–40	60–40	60–40	60–40
– % (sub) angular				

S31 – RB/B from Chlorakas-Palloures

S47 – RB/B from Kissonerga-Mosphilia

S73 – RB/B from Anbelikou-Agios Georghios

Fig. 4. Samples S31, S47 and S73 made with Fabric I as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

S26 – RB/B from Chlorakas-Palloures

S50 – RB/B from Kissonerga-Mosphilia

S52 – RB/B from Kissonerga-Mosphilia

Fig. 5. Samples S26, S50 and S52 made with Fabric II as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

4.3. Fabric III: Fabric with dominant presence of micritic limestone and chert

Fabric III, represented by 17 samples, is dominated by micritic limestone and chert fragments. All samples correspond to Spalled Ware and were recovered from all sites except Politiko-Kokkinorotsos, where this ware is absent. Micritic limestone fragments reach up to 5 mm in diameter, often containing microfossils, opaques, and quartz in their fine fraction. Chert fragments are smaller, typically under 0.8 mm.

Common inclusions include sandstone, serpentinite, monocrystalline

quartz, and opaques, along with basalt and polycrystalline quartz. In the fine fraction, argillaceous inclusions, mica, serpentinite, feldspars, and opaques are present. The presence of large inclusions, such as calcite grains (e.g., in sample S51 calcite grains reach 3 mm in diameter), along with elongated voids, indicates the use of minimally refined clay, likely containing these coarse inclusions and organic matter that burned out during firing (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Samples S37, S51 and S77 made with Fabric III as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

4.4. Fabric IV: Fabric with dominant presence of amphibole, feldspar, and quartz grains

Fabric IV is represented by five samples and is distinct for its amphibole-rich composition, with feldspar and quartz as significant components. All samples, derived from Chlorakas-Palloures, correspond to LChalRM ware. The fabric is moderately optically active, with a homogenous groundmass and a grey-to-black biscuit-textured core. Planar voids parallel to the section margins suggest the presence of organic inclusions in the clay. Amphibole dominates, with frequent feldspar (mainly plagioclase) and quartz. Less common inclusions comprise serpentine, olivine, dolerite, basalt, and sandstone. The relatively well-sorted inclusions suggest a more systematic material processing than that observed in the other fabrics (Fig. 7).

4.5. Fabric V: Fabric with dominant presence of carbonates

Fabric V, comprising of 10 samples, is dominated by carbonates such as microfossils, micritic limestone, and feldspars. All samples derive from Politiko-Kokkinorotsos and correspond to RL and RBL wares. Microfossils (predominantly foraminifera) dominate, some open and others calcite-filled, often coated with opaques or iron oxides. Micritic limestone fragments, containing microfossils, quartz, and feldspars (mainly plagioclase), are prevalent. The preservation of microfossil structures suggests low-temperature firing below the decomposition threshold of carbonaceous materials (Maggetti et al., 2011; Travé Allèpuz, 2021) (Fig. 8).

4.6. Fabric VI: Fabric with dominant presence of feldspars and dolerite

Fabric VI is characterised by the dominance of feldspar, polycrystalline quartz, and dolerite inclusions. It consists of 14 samples. All samples were sourced from Politiko-Kokkinorotsos and correspond to three macroscopically identified wares, i.e., RL, RBL, and CW. Dolerite fragments, often weathered, are relatively large, reaching up to 3 mm in diameter. Other observed inclusions include monocrystalline quartz, serpentine, clay pellets, opaques, and orthopyroxenes. Less common inclusions are olivine, basalt, clinopyroxenes, sandstone, micritic

limestone, and microfossils. In the fine fraction, feldspars, quartz, opaques, biotite, microfossils, and limestone are present (Fig. 9).

4.7. Fabric VII: Fabric with dominant presence of igneous rock fragments, especially dolerite and basalt

Lastly, Fabric VII is the second largest fabric group in the sample, consisting of 15 samples. All samples in this group are from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and correspond to three macroscopically identified wares, i.e., RL, CW, and RBL. This fabric is characterised by a dominance of dolerite and basalt fragments, with clinopyroxenes and feldspars (mainly plagioclase) present in large quantities. Quartz and opaques are also common, along with few amphibole grains and olivine (Fig. 10).

4.8. Outliers

In addition to the seven petrographic fabric groups, four samples stand out as outliers that cannot be assigned to any of the established groups. Outlier S49 originates from Kissonerga-Mosphilia and corresponds to the macroscopically identified RB/B ware. While similar to Fabric I, it is distinguished by its exclusively red to brown argillaceous inclusions, which exhibit visible microcracks and darker outlines. The uniform size and even distribution of these inclusions suggest intentional mixing into the clay, likely as temper, rather than their occurrence as natural components. This fabric shares compositional similarities with those described by Nodarou (2017) as Fabric Groups 8, 9, and 10, in the study of Late Bronze Age pitthoi from Alassa. It also shares similarities with Fabric IX, reported by Graham (2013: 296–297, Appendix 4) in Early-Middle Bronze Age ceramics from Kissonerga-Ammoudhia.

Outlier S71, sampled from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and corresponding to the RBL ware, shares mineralogical and technological characteristics with Fabric VII but differs in its inclusion of sedimentary components such as chert and sandstone, alongside igneous fragments like dolerite and basalt. Outlier S79, also from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, corresponds to the CW ware. It is defined by its dominance of basalt, clinopyroxenes, and quartz, distinguishing it from the main fabric groups. Finally, Outlier S80, sampled from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, is characterised by the prominent presence of radiolarian

Fig. 7. Samples S41, S43 and S45 made with Fabric IV as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

Fig. 8. Samples S4, S8 and S14 made with Fabric V as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

Fig. 9. Samples S3, S5 and S6 made with Fabric VI as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

Fig. 10. Samples S58, S61 and S65 made with Fabric VII as defined by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

chert, orthopyroxenes, and micritic limestone, further highlighting its distinctiveness within the overall assemblage.

The study of outliers is important as these atypical samples reveal aspects of production, distribution, and technological choices that challenge and expand what is considered standard within the larger compositional clusters. By examining petrographic outliers, i.e., samples that could not be assigned to any of the defined fabric groups based on the characteristics of their clay matrix, including the type, density, and distribution of plastic and aplastic constituents, we gain insights into a broader range of practices, and refine our understanding of regional ceramic traditions, offering a more nuanced perspective on compositional and technological variation (Fig. 11).

5. Elemental analysis of selected samples using hhXRF

In addition to ceramic petrography, 80 samples were analysed using handheld energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (hhXRF) to determine their bulk geochemical composition. The Hitachi X-MET8000 Expert GEO handheld XRF analyser, owned by the Archaeological Science Laboratories of the Cyprus Institute, was employed for this study. Analysis was performed on fresh flat sections of the ceramic body, avoiding large inclusions, voids, slip layers, and post-depositional encrustations. Each sample was analysed using an 8 mm spot size for 120 s

in both mining and soil modes. The reference standard SARM69 (MINTEK 2000; Jacobson et al., 2002), in the form of a pressed-powder pellet, was measured at the beginning, midpoint, and end of each analytical day to ensure precision.

Elements were excluded from further processing if their concentrations were below the detection limit, showed poor reproducibility, or had relative errors exceeding 20 %. Principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted on both raw and log-transformed data to explore relationships among samples, revealing consistent groupings across both approaches. It was, hence, decided to continue data processing and integration using the raw data that represent the original values (Table 7), as it was easier to interpret, assessing the direct relationship between the variables without the impact of transformation.

Datasets with and without calcium (Ca) were analysed to assess its impact on sample groupings. Calcium is one of the most common elements and a major component in many rocks. PCA results indicated no significant differences, suggesting calcium's influence on groupings was negligible. This supported its exclusion from subsequent analyses to focus on elements with greater relevance to ceramic composition. Strontium (Sr) was also excluded due to its strong positive correlation with Ca; they have similar geochemical behaviour as both can substitute in calcium-bearing minerals like feldspars or carbonates. To enhance the total variance captured by the principal components, zinc (Zn) and

Fig. 11. S49 (a), S71 (b), S79(c), and S80 (d), defined as outliers by petrographic analysis (photomicrographs taken under XPL, scale bar size: 0.5 mm).

barium (Ba) were also excluded in subsequent data processing rounds. Their removal was justified by their low concentrations, which limited their contribution to sample differentiation.

For final interpretations, PCA was performed on 10 elements to uncover patterns among 80 samples (excluding sample 76, which was too small for proper analysis). The final dataset included Mg, Al, Si (mining mode), and K, Ti, Mn, Fe, Ni, Cu, and Zr (soil mode) (Table 7). A correlation matrix with an unrotated solution and eigenvalues > 1 was employed, with up to 25 iterations for convergence. The first two principal components, explaining 50.8 % of the total variance, were used for graphical scatterplots. The third component, accounting for 16.1 % of the variance, was not considered informative for data interpretation. A relatively good correspondence was observed between petrographic and elemental groupings (Fig. 12), reinforcing the identification of compositional clusters and their regional provenance.

Clear distinctions emerged between the Paphian fabrics and those from the northern Troodos foothills (Figs. 13 and 14). These differences must reflect both the diverse geological environments from which raw materials were sourced and the existence of distinct regional ceramic traditions. While we acknowledge that geological variation influences the composition of ceramic fabrics, it does not automatically imply intentional cultural choices in pottery production, as factors such as resource availability and functional requirements may also play a role.

Iron (Fe) and copper (Cu) were higher in samples associated with igneous-derived fabrics (IV–VII), characterised by inclusions of volcanic and plutonic rocks such as basalt, dolerite, and gabbro (Cohen et al., 2011) (Fig. 12). These rocks, rich in ferromagnesian minerals, influence the elevated levels of Fe, magnesium (Mg), and trace metals in the ceramics made from derived clays. Conversely, higher levels of potassium (K), nickel (Ni), and zirconium (Zr) typified Paphian fabrics (I–III). Potassium, linked to mica in clay-rich inclusions (Cohen et al., 2011: 36), reflects the argillaceous materials of the Mamonia terrane.

Fabric group IV, identified at Chlorakas-Palloures (Table 7), is differentiated by the presence of amphibole grains (Fig. 12). Amphiboles, commonly found in mafic and ultramafic rocks of the Troodos ophiolite, influence the mineralogical and elemental composition of ceramics. These amphibole-bearing clays likely formed from the mixing

of ophiolitic and sedimentary deposits, contributing to elevated Fe, Mg, and trace elements typical of these minerals. Samples from this group plot closer to Troodos fabrics in elemental analyses (Figs. 13 and 14), reflecting their intermediate composition.

Based on the hhXRF data, the ceramic sample from Politiko-Kokkinorotsos exhibits the largest compositional variability (Figs. 13 and 14). The Politiko samples are more dispersed on the scatterplots compared to the more tightly clustered fabric groups from other sites. This greater variability could be linked to the site's identification as a hunting station (Webb et al., 2009), where the mode of organisation of pottery production may have differed from that of the more permanently settled communities. The transient nature of occupation could have led to a more flexible approach to raw material selection and manufacturing practices, resulting in a broader compositional spread. However, these remain preliminary observations, and more evidence is needed to support more concrete arguments.

6. Discussion: Integrating macroscopic, petrographic and elemental data

The macroscopic, petrographic and chemical analyses of the data shed light to pottery production during the Late Chalcolithic. This compositional study is the first of its kind when it comes to comparing Late Chalcolithic pottery, integrating macroscopic, petrographic and elemental analyses of datasets from across the island.

A very important outcome of this study is the confirmation that the most popular wares at each site seem to be indeed locally produced. The first three fabric groups (Fabric I, II and III) and the outlier S49 contain the same types of inclusions, a combination of argillaceous inclusions, sandstone fragments, carbonates and chert, and more rarely igneous rocks. All three fabrics share a similar colour range (light orange to dark brown), and the moderate optical activity of the clay matrices suggests similar textural or structural features in the clay matrices, which could imply similar mineralogical compositions or firing conditions. In addition, the three fabrics exhibit poorly sorted inclusions with a bimodal grain size distribution, hinting at similar clay preparation methods or tempering practices.

Table 7

Raw elemental data obtained from hhXRF analysis of the 80 ceramic samples under study.

Sample id.	Site	Ware	Shape	Petrofabric	Mining mode			Soil mode			Mn (ppm)	Fe	Ni (ppm)	Cu (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Sr (ppm)	Zr (ppm)	Ba (ppm)
					Mg	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti								
S1	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	bowl	VI	2.6	8.6	25.4	0.6	2.8	0.6	1623	10.0	48.0	200	167	491	118	734
S2	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	jar	VI	3.3	9.6	24.1	0.6	1.5	0.6	1029	8.6	21.7	218	106	116	72	158
S3	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	jar	VI	3.3	9.8	23.0	1.1	3.8	0.5	1966	9.1	55.3	231	153	167	108	234
S4	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	jar	V	3.1	7.5	21.7	2.2	11.0	0.4	3354	7.0	82.0	96	98	769	76	873
S5	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	jar	VI	2.5	9.0	26.6	0.8	2.1	0.6	1075	8.9	40.0	178	199	415	121	579
S6	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	jar	VI	2.1	9.2	26.7	0.8	1.7	0.5	1454	7.9	40.7	120	226	213	101	556
S7	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RL	jar	VI	2.4	8.7	27.9	0.7	1.5	0.5	1773	7.5	32.7	121	226	250	78	673
S8	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	V	2.4	6.7	20.2	1.3	6.2	0.2	8897	4.1	44.0	63	50	377	43	671
S9	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	VI	4.2	9.0	26.4	0.8	1.9	0.5	1085	9.3	47.0	162	103	371	74	331
S10	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	VI	2.7	8.4	26.0	0.4	1.8	0.5	1218	7.0	32.7	77	47	220	88	576
S11	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	V	3.4	8.8	24.3	1.2	3.8	0.4	1840	6.1	49.7	104	80	292	69	393
S12	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	VI	3.0	9.8	24.7	0.5	2.1	0.6	1391	8.8	36.0	164	146	355	91	285
S13	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	VI	2.7	9.0	26.5	0.5	2.0	0.5	1115	7.7	36.3	93	53	354	93	355
S14	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	V	2.9	6.6	21.1	1.1	16.2	0.3	2283	4.8	96.3	104	75	996	84	992
S15	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	V	3.6	7.6	21.9	0.8	10.0	0.2	1341	2.8	43.0	45	42	386	45	459
S16	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	VI	3.3	9.0	23.3	1.1	5.3	0.5	1821	7.3	53.3	161	132	352	89	309
S17	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	VI	2.5	8.9	23.9	0.5	1.7	0.5	1534	8.7	32.7	169	156	269	87	411
S18	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	V	3.1	6.4	19.9	1.4	14.9	0.3	5766	5.2	88.3	92	79	700	79	665
S19	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	jar	V	3.0	7.8	22.2	0.5	5.8	0.4	1666	6.9	54.7	96	87	449	69	1203
S20	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	V	3.0	8.8	22.3	0.7	6.8	0.5	1960	7.9	43.5	143	124	292	79	249
S21	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	RBL	bowl	V	3.5	7.1	20.3	1.3	8.5	0.2	2654	4.0	56.5	62	55	349	66	450
S22	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	CW	pan/tray	VI	3.2	5.8	17.6	0.7	1.6	0.3	968	4.8	40.3	126	75	170	56	223
S23	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	CW	pan/tray	VI	2.6	7.7	26.3	0.5	1.8	0.4	1379	6.4	23.7	217	116	206	68	184
S24	Politiko-Kokkinorotsos	CW	pan/tray	VI	3.3	9.5	24.4	0.6	2.4	0.6	1657	8.7	42.0	271	165	278	111	211
S25	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	I	5.5	9.1	26.0	1.0	1.6	0.5	560	4.8	187.5	43	78	113	142	108
S26	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	II	4.4	8.4	24.3	1.0	7.1	0.5	821	5.6	212.0	50	103	243	167	219
S27	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	II	1.6	9.1	28.2	0.9	5.9	0.4	832	4.6	134.3	47	80	201	130	169
S28	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	I	1.5	9.9	27.7	1.1	1.6	0.5	2024	6.6	89.3	35	109	211	165	215
S29	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	I	1.3	9.4	29.3	0.9	2.3	0.4	3303	4.8	83.3	64	100	128	123	169
S30	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	I	1.7	8.8	26.3	1.0	3.1	0.4	597	6.3	75.0	66	97	152	151	160
S31	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	I	1.6	10.1	27.3	1.0	2.0	0.5	777	6.7	85.7	234	101	182	176	178
S32	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	I	1.5	9.6	27.6	1.5	3.0	0.6	1900	8.4	104.7	168	130	255	238	269
S33	Chlorakas-Palloures	RB/B	bowl	II	3.9	7.2	20.8	1.3	3.0	0.6	1274	6.2	253.0	64	105	163	201	145
S34	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	jar	III	2.5	7.8	28.4	1.8	6.0	0.5	936	4.7	96.3	54	90	303	189	298
S35	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	bowl	III	1.5	9.5	27.5	0.8	3.2	0.4	989	4.6	61.3	65	86	102	133	164
S36	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	bowl	III	2.4	8.1	28.8	1.7	4.1	0.5	943	4.4	79.0	44	84	205	173	254
S37	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	bowl	III	2.5	7.9	27.3	1.5	3.8	0.4	904	3.8	76.7	49	70	153	142	178
S38	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	jar	III	2.8	6.2	25.5	1.3	9.1	0.4	1380	3.8	77.0	46	67	243	136	208
S39	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	jar	III	2.5	7.4	28.6	1.6	4.1	0.5	822	4.2	83.3	43	77	269	159	242
S40	Chlorakas-Palloures	SW	bowl	III	2.8	8.0	27.8	1.3	6.6	0.4	1034	3.8	83.7	50	74	194	136	193
S41	Chlorakas-Palloures	LChalRM	jar	IV	6.2	7.6	25.1	0.8	2.8	0.2	1224	8.5	248.0	372	57	351	38	218
S42	Chlorakas-Palloures	LChalRM	jar	IV	3.3	8.9	24.1	0.8	2.1	0.3	1777	9.6	111.0	153	222	358	46	277
S43	Chlorakas-Palloures	LChalRM	bowl	IV	3.7	8.6	25.6	0.8	3.8	0.3	736	7.2	67.3	68	35	287	55	159
S44	Chlorakas-Palloures	LChalRM	jar	IV	5.8	7.4	27.0	0.6	2.1	0.3	1281	7.4	85.0	174	210	410	39	199
S45	Chlorakas-Palloures	LChalRM	jar	IV	5.6	7.5	23.2	0.5	1.7	0.1	869	5.2	175.7	70	34	188	21	104
S46	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	RB/B	bowl	II	4.6	8.7	26.6	0.6	1.7	0.3	755	3.5	121.5	42	53	92	79	108
S47	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	RB/B	bowl	I	1.2	9.4	29.4	1.0	0.7	0.5	2006	5.7	53.7	45	77	255	152	158
S48	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	RB/B	bowl	II	1.6	9.9	28.4	1.2	0.5	0.5	248	6.3	69.3	65	93	208	157	175
S49	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	RB/B	bowl	Outlier	1.1	9.3	29.3	0.9	1.1	0.5	1513	6.0	77.7	44	91	293	167	206
S50	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	RB/B	bowl	II	5.3	8.1	25.9	1.0	2.9	0.6	699	6.3	301.3	56	94	168	162	147
S51	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	SW	bowl	III	4.2	8.6	26.9	1.2	3.7	0.8	2154	6.9	235.0	54	125	210	203	214
S52	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	SW	jar	II	1.9	6.9	26.9	1.3	6.4	0.4	745	3.6	86.0	50	66	211	147	260
S53	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	SW	jar	III	5.0	8.3	26.1	0.9	2.2	0.6	857	6.1	261.7	83	99	306	176	234

(continued on next page)

Table 7 (continued)

Sample id.	Site	Ware	Shape	Petrofabric	Mining mode			Soil mode				Mn (ppm)	Fe	Ni (ppm)	Cu (ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Sr (ppm)	Zr (ppm)	Ba (ppm)
					Mg	Al	Si	K	Ca	Ti									
S54	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	SW	jar	III	2.3	7.1	27.7	1.5	6.6	0.4	1098	4.4	103.3	53	80	254	172	331	
S55	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	SW	jar	III	4.7	8.3	27.1	1.2	2.7	0.6	733	6.0	264.0	66	95	162	167	123	
S56	Kissonerga-Mosphilia	SW	jar	III	4.5	7.6	27.9	1.2	2.3	0.7	660	6.4	267.8	55	112	179	183	139	
S57	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	3.0	9.6	25.7	0.8	1.3	0.5	1202	7.4	32.7	317	107	92	99	123	
S58	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	3.5	8.9	25.7	0.8	1.5	0.3	1135	5.8	26.0	280	85	73	50	107	
S59	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	2.7	9.0	26.7	1.1	1.4	0.5	1256	7.8	37.3	397	102	107	93	129	
S60	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	jar	VII	2.6	9.1	25.8	1.1	1.4	0.5	1544	9.2	40.7	529	117	120	99	130	
S61	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	3.4	7.6	24.3	1.0	1.7	0.5	1337	8.9	38.7	360	229	166	81	103	
S62	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	3.8	9.6	25.7	0.7	0.8	0.2	720	4.5	22.0	77	61	79	32	0	
S63	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	2.7	9.2	26.9	0.7	1.0	0.4	1276	5.9	28.3	95	173	137	101	194	
S64	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RBL	bowl	VII	2.7	9.6	26.0	0.8	1.4	0.6	1569	9.4	43.0	311	141	111	117	138	
S65	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RBL	bowl	VII	2.5	9.8	26.0	1.1	0.8	0.5	1734	7.8	41.7	92	233	90	109	164	
S66	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RBL	bowl	VII	3.4	8.9	25.7	1.2	1.5	0.5	1873	8.3	39.3	147	347	241	89	142	
S67	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RBL	bowl	VII	2.1	9.3	26.6	0.6	0.8	0.5	1472	8.8	33.0	158	235	80	93	117	
S68	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RBL	bowl	VII	3.7	9.5	24.8	1.4	1.5	0.4	1090	7.5	38.0	169	133	269	67	117	
S69	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	3.2	9.3	26.7	0.7	0.9	0.3	1098	5.9	25.7	127	156	58	50	0	
S70	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	VII	3.1	10.5	24.6	1.7	0.9	0.4	2907	9.0	31.3	223	1167	70	59	259	
S71	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RL	bowl	Outlier	2.8	9.0	25.4	1.1	2.3	0.4	682	7.8	18.5	238	189	232	58	221	
S72	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RB/B	bowl	I	1.8	10.1	28.3	1.1	1.3	0.6	1612	6.6	77.0	76	107	163	172	198	
S73	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	RB/B	bowl	I	2.9	8.5	28.8	0.9	0.7	0.5	550	4.9	113.3	79	77	98	127	110	
S74	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	SW	jar	III	2.7	7.3	29.7	1.9	1.7	0.4	1363	7.9	34.7	222	191	116	67	105	
S75	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	SW	jar	III	2.5	7.8	28.0	1.5	5.5	0.4	1084	4.4	96.0	72	79	214	157	184	
S77	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	SW	jar	III	3.0	8.1	28.7	1.4	3.3	0.4	918	3.7	69.0	54	68	163	129	141	
S78	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	SW	jar	III	2.9	7.5	23.9	1.6	4.2	0.4	1043	4.1	85.0	59	87	304	153	178	
S79	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	CW	pan/tray	Outlier	3.7	8.9	25.5	1.7	4.1	0.4	894	4.4	93.0	152	83	184	162	210	
S80	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	CW	pan/tray	Outlier	3.8	8.5	25.2	1.2	1.3	0.4	1993	7.1	31.7	186	196	114	66	123	
S81	Ambelikou-Agios Georghios	CW	pan/tray	VII	3.4	9.1	25.2	1.2	1.1	0.5	1374	7.8	44.7	317	156	122	104	115	

Fig. 12. PCA scatterplot using the hhXRF dataset. Samples labelled according to petrographic fabric.

Fig. 13. PCA scatterplot using the hhXRF dataset. Samples labelled according to site of recovery.

Fig. 14. PCA scatterplot using the hhXRF dataset. Samples labelled according to regional traditions as identified in the analysis.

The presence of common planar voids, particularly in Fabric III, as well as similar inclusions found in Fabrics I and III, may indicate the use of similar pottery-making practices. These features could result from shared techniques, such as how the clay was kneaded, which could influence the formation of voids or the distribution of inclusions. Additionally, these characteristics might be a reflection of similar drying and firing conditions, where factors such as temperature, humidity, or firing atmosphere could have contributed to the development of these specific textural features across the different fabrics. It is, therefore, suggested that these fabrics represent a common tradition that characterises southwestern Cyprus during the Late Chalcolithic period. The elemental data reinforce this argument as there is a clear chemical cluster that differentiates Paphian samples from those deriving from northwestern and central Cyprus. Interestingly, all the samples that belong to the macroscopically identified ware RB/B belong to the petrographic Fabric I or Fabric II. Similarly, all SW samples have been produced in Fabric III, a micritic limestone and chert-rich fabric. This correlation between these wares and fabrics could be suggestive of functional and/or stylistic considerations in production. For example, RB/B occurs mainly in thin-walled bowls and pouring vessels like spouted jugs, while the SW occurs in closed vessels like storage jars and flasks.

The combination of rocks and minerals in the composition of Fabrics I to III aligns well with the local geo-environment. The closest river to Kissonerga, the Mavrokolymbos River ([Geological Survey Department, 1995](#)), traverses a geologically diverse landscape that reflects the varied mineralogical characteristics observed in these fabrics. The river flows through sedimentary formations, including chalks, marls, and calcarenites, with contributions from the Aghios Photios Group, which includes sandstones, siltstones, mudstones, and calcarenites. It also passes areas with terra rossa soils and Quaternary deposits. In some stretches, the river cuts through igneous and metamorphic exposures, including the serpentinite sequence, highlighting the geological diversity of the region ([Kluyver, 1969](#); [Hadjistavrinou and Afrodisis, 1977](#); [Cohen et al., 2011](#)).

Fabric IV recorded at Chlorakas-Palloures and composed exclusively by LChalRM samples deviates from the aforementioned ceramic traditions. Fabric IV is characterised by the dominant presence of amphibole grains, as well as other ophiolitic inclusions, and the limited presence of carbonates, a yellow to dark orange and brown matrix with moderately optically active clay, well-sorted inclusions, and a bimodal grain distribution. Its composition suggests careful clay processing that it is not met in the aforementioned fabrics. The initial morphological analysis suggested that these vessels originated elsewhere, as they are stylistically and morphologically distinct from RB/B and SW wares. This hypothesis is corroborated by petrographic analysis. These sherds bear a strong resemblance to the main Late Chalcolithic ware found further to the west, particularly in the Polis region, at sites such as Makounta-Voules ([Maliszewski, 2013](#); [Grossman et al., 2018](#)). However, as no analytical data are available from this region, it is important to note that this hypothesis is primarily based on morphological and stylistic comparisons. In that area, the Makounta-Kseropotamos River ([Geological Survey Department, 1995](#)) traverses geological formations primarily associated with the Troodos Ophiolite complex, characterised by igneous rocks such as basalt, gabbro, and dolerite, with sedimentary deposits appearing only in the lower reaches of their courses.

The ceramic samples recovered from Politiko-Kokkinorotsos are classified into two petrographic fabrics: Fabric V and Fabric VI. The primary distinction between these fabrics lies in their mineralogical composition. Fabric V is characterised by a predominance of carbonates, including calcite and microfossils, whereas Fabric VI is marked by a dominance of feldspar, polycrystalline quartz grains, and fragments of dolerite. Both fabrics were utilised in the production of RL and RBL pottery, corresponding to the macroscopic Fabric A, B, and D as defined by [Webb et al. \(2009\)](#). Notably, CW samples collected from Politiko are associated exclusively with Fabric VI. The identification of at least two distinct fabric recipes at the site raises significant questions regarding

the organisation of pottery production, particularly in the context of the site's seasonal occupation.

The composition of these two fabrics, characterised by the presence of igneous rocks and associated minerals such as dolerite, serpentinite, orthopyroxenes, as well as minor amounts of basalt and clinopyroxenes, strongly indicates that the raw materials were sourced from the foothills of the Troodos Mountain Range. This region is renowned for its ophiolitic components, which are among its most distinctive geological features ([Searle, 1969](#)). The presence of carbonates in Fabric V suggests a deliberate mixture of materials during its production—a technological choice that sets it apart from the co-existing Fabric VI.

The Pediaios River passes near Politiko ([Geological Survey Department, 1995](#)). As the longest river in Cyprus, it originates in the Troodos Mountains and flows north-eastward through a variety of geological environments. It traverses the Troodos ophiolite, characterised by igneous rocks such as basalt, gabbro, dolerite, and serpentinite, which dominate the river's headwaters and contribute minerals to its sediment load. As the river descends into the Mesaoria Plain, it cuts through sedimentary formations including marls, chalks, and limestones, which frequently contain fossils and carbonates ([Gass, 1960](#); [Searle, 1969](#); [Bear, 1975](#)). At this stage, there is no evidence to determine whether pottery associated with the seasonal camp at Kokkinorotsos was produced on-site or elsewhere. The sediment materials from these environments are reflected in Fabrics V and VI, which could have been produced anywhere along the Troodos northern foothills, supplying the seasonal camp at Politiko as well. On the other hand, several studies (e.g., [Eerkens 2008](#); [Gibbs and Jordan 2013](#); [Sturm et al. 2016](#); [Kulkova et al. 2023](#)) provide evidence that seasonal occupation allows for in-situ pottery production suggesting that local manufacture remains a possibility.

Almost all sherds from Ambelikou-Agios Georghios have been classified as belonging to Fabric VII. This includes all RL and RBL samples, as well as one CW sample. Exceptions include the RB/B and SW samples, along with three outliers. Despite these exceptions, both Fabric VII and the three outliers contain similar inclusions dominated by igneous components, strongly suggesting local production using materials sourced from the nearby Kampos or Xeros River valleys ([Geological Survey Department, 1995](#)). These rivers, located approximately 3 km west and 5 km east of the modern village of Ambelikou, respectively, originate in the Troodos Mountains. The geological influence of the Troodos is evident in the strong presence of igneous inclusions within the clay's composition.

This study has confirmed the presence of Paphian RB/B and SW wares at Ambelikou-Agios Georghios, an important outcome that supports the circulation of pottery (and potentially many more other commodities) beyond the topographical areas traditionally associated with these ceramic traditions. The selected RB/B and SW samples align perfectly with Fabric I and Fabric III, respectively, and correspond stylistically and morphologically to Paphian RB/B and SW wares, leaving little doubt about their production in the southwestern of the island.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides a comprehensive analysis of Late Chalcolithic pottery production in Cyprus, revealing distinct regional traditions and localised production practices. The integration of macroscopic, mineralogical and chemical data has shown that the most common wares were locally produced, with three major fabric groups (I, II, and III) exhibiting shared mineral compositions and firing techniques, suggesting a unified tradition in southwestern Cyprus.

Notably, variations in Fabric IV, from the Polis region, indicate a departure from local practices, highlighting potential interregional connections. The identification of Paphian pottery at Ambelikou-Agios Georghios and the presence of regional wares at Chlorakas-Palloures further support the idea of interaction and interconnection between different parts of the island. This study underscores the significance of

pottery production as a marker of socioeconomic and cultural interactions among the Late Chalcolithic communities. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the intra-insular dynamics (e.g. Bolger, 1987; 2007; Bolger and Peltenburg, 2014; Peltenburg, 2018) leading into the Bronze Age, providing a foundation for future research into Cyprus' ceramic traditions and broader societal shifts. This work represents the first comprehensive assessment of Late Chalcolithic pottery production across the island, integrating macroscopic, petrographic, and chemical data, and lays a crucial foundation for future studies to expand on, furthering the exploration of regional and temporal variations in Cyprus' ceramic heritage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Maria Hadjigavriel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maria Dikomitou Eliadou:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This study was conducted within the framework of the PlaCe-ITN project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 956410. Ceramic thin section preparation and hhXRF analysis were carried out at the Archaeological Science Laboratories, Science and Technology in Archaeology and Culture Research Center (STARC) of the Cyprus Institute. Colour readings on sherd cross-sections were documented using a Munsell RM200 portable handheld digital colour matching Capsure instrument, owned by STARC, Cyprus Institute. Access to SPSS software was provided by the Faculty of Archaeology at Leiden University. The final photomicrographs for publication were taken using the ZEISS Axiolab 5 optical polarising microscope with an Axiocam 208 colour camera, also owned by STARC, Cyprus Institute, and the Leica DM1750 M optical polarising microscope, owned by the Cyprus American Archaeological Research Institute (CAARI) in Nicosia. We are deeply grateful to the directors and staff of these institutes for their generous support and for providing access to the necessary instrumentation and software. Special thanks are also extended to Ermina Emmanouel for her support in preparing the illustrations for this paper and to Dr Artemis Georgiou for the creation of the map in Fig. 1 with digital data of the Cyprus Geological Survey Department.

Our sincere thanks go to Prof. Bleda Düring, Dr Diane Bolger, Prof. Jennifer Webb, and Prof. David Frankel for entrusting us with the material included in this study. We extend our heartfelt thanks to the Directors of the Department of Antiquities, Dr Marina Solomidou-Ieronymidou and Dr Giorgos Georgiou, for granting us permission to study, sample, and publish the ceramic material under investigation, and to the staff of the Cyprus Museum, Larnaca Museum, and Paphos Museum for facilitating our work, as well as for their assistance during the selection and export of samples for analysis. Finally, we sincerely thank the anonymous reviewers for their valuable feedback and constructive comments, which have significantly contributed to improving the quality of this paper. Any remaining errors or omissions are solely the responsibility of the authors.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Arnold, D.E., 2000. Does the standardization of ceramic pastes really mean specialization? *J. Archaeol. Method Theory* 7 (4), 333–375.
- Bear, L.M., (1975). *The geology and mineral resources of the Akaki-Lythrodondha area*. Geological Survey Department Cyprus, Memoir no. 3. Nicosia: Government Printing office, Cyprus.
- Bolger, D. (1987). Is there a western Cyprus? A Chalcolithic viewpoint. In D. W. Rupp (Ed.), *Western Cyprus: Connections* (pp. 69–81). Paul Åströms Förlag. (Studies in Mediterranean Archaeology, 77).
- Bolger, D., 2007. Cultural interactions in third millennium BC Cyprus: Evidence of ceramics. In: Antoniadou, S., Pace, A. (Eds.), *Mediterranean Crossroads*. Pierides Foundation, pp. 164–188.
- Bolger, D., 2013. Matter of choice: Cypriot interactions with the Levantine mainland during the late 4th–3rd millennium BC. *Levant* 45 (1), 1–18.
- Bolger, D., Webb, J., 2013. Ceramics. In: Peltenburg, E. (Ed.), *Associated Regional Chronologies for the Ancient Near East and the Eastern Mediterranean ARCAE II Cyprus*. Brepols Publishers, pp. 39–127.
- Bolger, D., & Peltenburg, E. (2014). Material and social transformations in third millennium Cyprus: Evidence of ceramics. In J. Webb (Ed.), *Structure, measurement and meaning: Studies on prehistoric Cyprus in honour of David Frankel* (pp. 187–197). Paul Åströms Förlag. (Studies in Mediterranean Archaeology, 143).
- Bolger, D., Maguire, L., Quye, A., Ritson, S., & Stephen, F. M. K. (1998). The pottery. In E. Peltenburg (Ed.), *Lemba Archaeological Project II.1A: Excavations at Kissonerga-Mosphilia 1979–1992* (pp. 93–147). Paul Åströms Förlag. (Studies in Mediterranean Archaeology, 70, 2).
- Cohen, D., Morisseau, E., Rutherford, N., Zissimos, A., 2011. *Geochemical atlas of Cyprus*. UNSW Press.
- Darvill, T., 2008. *Oxford Concise Dictionary of Archaeology*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Dikaio, P. (1962). The Stone Age. In P. Dikaio & J. R. Stewart (Eds.), *The Stone Age and the Early Bronze Age in Cyprus* (pp. 1–204). Swedish Cyprus Expedition. (Swedish Cyprus Expedition IV:1A).
- Dikomitou-Eliadou, M., Georgiou, A. (2024). Ceramics: Stylistic and Functional Analysis. In: Nikita, E., Rehren, T. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Archaeology*, 2nd Edition, vol. 2, 378–385, London: Academic Press.
- Dikomitou Eliadou, Kiriati, E., 2023. Chapter 18: Sampling for ceramic analysis. In: *Handbook on field sampling for laboratory analysis in archaeology*, 153–164. H2020 Twinning project 'PROMISED'. The Cyprus Institute, Nicosia.
- Dobres, M.A., 1999. Technology's links and chaînes. The processual unfolding of technique and technician. In: Dobres, M.A., Hoffman, C.R. (Eds.), *The Social Dynamics of Technology: Practice, Politics and World Views*. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, pp. 124–146.
- Dobres, M.A., 2010. Archaeologies of technology. *Camb. J. Econ.* 34 (1), 103–114.
- Düring, B. S., Klínenberg, V., Sonnemann, T., Paraskeva, C., Croft, P., & Souter, E. (2019). Excavations at Chlorakas-Palloures: New light on Chalcolithic Cyprus. *Report of the Department of Antiquities New Series*, 2018, 467–490.
- Düring, B.S., De Ceuster, S., Degryse, P., Kassianidou, V., 2021. Transformative copper metallurgy in Chalcolithic Cyprus: A reappraisal. *Antiquity* 95 (381), 670–685.
- Eerkens, J.W., 2008. Nomadic Potters Relationships between Ceramic Technologies and Mobility Strategies. In: Hans, B., Wendrich, W. (Eds.), *The Archaeology of Mobility: Old World and New World Nomadism*. Cotsen Institute of Archaeology Press at UCLA, pp. 307–326.
- Foster, N., Grave, P., Vickery, N., Kealhofer, L., 2011. Non-destructive analysis using PXRF: Methodology and application to archaeological ceramics. *X-Ray Spectrom.* 40, 389–398.
- Frahm, E., Doonan, R.C.P., 2013. The technological versus methodological revolution of portable XRF in archaeology. *J. Archaeol. Sci.* 40, 1425–1434.
- Gass, I.G., 1960. *The Geology and Mineral Resources of the Dhali Area*. Geological Survey Department Cyprus, Memoir 4. Authority of the Government of Cyprus, London.
- Geological Survey Department of Cyprus. (1995). *Geological map of Cyprus*. Ministry of Agriculture, Natural Resources and Environment, Government of Cyprus.
- Gibbs, K., Jordan, P., 2013. Bridging the Boreal Forest Siberian Archaeology and the Emergence of Pottery among Prehistoric Hunter-Gatherers of Northern Eurasia. *Sibirica* 12 (1), 1–38.
- Gjerstad, E. (1980). The origin and chronology of the Early Bronze Age in Cyprus. *Report of the Department of Antiquities*, 1980, 1–16.
- Graham, L., 2013. *The necropolis of Kissonerga-Ammoudhia: Techniques of ceramic production in Early-Middle Bronze Age Western Cyprus*. University of Edinburgh [Unpublished doctoral dissertation].
- Grossman, K., Paulette, T., Graham, L., & McCarthy, A. (2018). Prehistoric archaeology in the Polis region: Survey and geophysics at Makounta-Voules and Stroumpi-Pigi-Agios Andronikos, Cyprus. Paper presented at the 11th International Congress on the Archaeology of the Ancient Near East (ICAANE), Munich.
- Hadjigavriel, M., 2019. *Connectivity through pottery horizons: Tracing interactions in Late Chalcolithic Cyprus*. Leiden University [Unpublished master's dissertation].
- Hadjigavriel, M., 2021. A tale of red and black: Reconstructing transfer of knowledge in Late Chalcolithic Cyprus. *Archaeological Review from Cambridge* 35 (2), 80–97.
- Hadjistavrinou, Y., Afrodisis, S., 1977. Geology and hydrogeology of the Paphos Region. *Bulletin of the Geological Survey Department, Cyprus* 7, 1–44.

- Hobsbawm, E.J. and T. Ranger (eds.) (1983). *The Invention of Tradition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jacobson, L., Van der Westhuizen, W. A., & Oosthuysen, J. (2002). SARM69 Ceramic-1: A new pottery certified reference material for inter- and intra-laboratory calibration. In E. Jerem & T. Biró (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 31st International Symposium on Archaeometry*. Archaeopress – Archaeolingua, BAR.
- Kluyver, H.M., 1969. Report on the Regional Geological Mapping in Paphos District. *Bulletin of the Geological Survey Department, Cyprus* 4, 21–36.
- Kulkova, M.A., Kashuba, M.T., Kulkov, A.M., 2023. Pottery Phenomenon in the Early mounted Nomad communities (“Cimmerian”) in the Northern Pontic region. *Arkheologiiia Evraziiskikh Stepei (archaeology of the Eurasian Steppes)* 4, 280–293.
- Maggetti, M., Neururer, Ch., Ramseyer, D., 2011. Temperature evolution inside a pot during experimental surface (bonfire) firing. *Appl. Clay Sci.* 53, 500–508.
- Maliszewski, D. (2013). *Chalcolithic and Bronze Age Pottery from the Field Survey in Northwestern Cyprus, 1992-1999*. Archaeopress (British Archaeological Reports International Series 2547).
- Mintek, 2000. SARM 69 Certificate of Analysis: Ceramic-1. Randburg. MINTEK, South Africa.
- Nodarou, E. (2017), Appendix X. An Analytical Study of the Pithoi from Alassa. In P. Keswani, S. Hadjisavvas & A. Jacobs (Eds.), *Alassa: Excavations at the Late Bronze Age Sites of Pano Mantilaris and Paliotaverna 1984-2000* (pp. 629-642). Department of Antiquities Cyprus.
- Paraskeva, C., 2017. Disentangling Past Narratives: A Reconsideration of Fyllia (Philia) Drakos Sites B and C. In: Pilides, D., Mina, M. (Eds.), *Four Decades of Hiatus in Archaeological Research in Cyprus: towards Restoring the Balance*. Verlag Holzhausen GmbH, pp. 72–91.
- Peltenburg, E., 1991. Towards a definition of the Late Chalcolithic in Cyprus: The monochrome pottery debate. In: Barlow, J., Bolger, D., Kling, B. (Eds.), *Cypriot Ceramics: Reading the Prehistoric Record*. University of Pennsylvania, pp. 9–20.
- Peltenburg, E. (1998). *Excavations at Kissonerga-Mosphilia 1979-1992. Lemba Archaeological Project II.IA*. Studies in Mediterranean Archaeology, 70(2). Paul Åströms Förlag.
- Peltenburg, E. (Ed.) (2003). *Lemba Archaeological Project III:1 The Colonisation and Settlement of Cyprus: Investigations at Kissonerga-Mylouthkia 1976-1996*. Paul Åströms Förlag (Studies in Mediterranean Archaeology 70, 4).
- Peltenburg, E. (2000). *Excavations at Kissonerga-Mosphilia 1979-1992* [Data set]. York: Archaeology Data Service. <https://doi.org/10.5284/1000331>.
- Peltenburg, E., 2018. The Entry of Cyprus Into the Circum-Aegean World and the Growth of Regionalism on the Island. In: Dietz, S., Mavridis, F., Tankosić, Ž., Takaoğlu, T. (Eds.), *Communities in Transition: the Circum-Aegean Area in the 5th and 4th Millennia BC*. Oxbow Books, pp. 458–467.
- Roux, V., 2016. Ceramic manufacture: the chaîne opératoire approach. In: Hunt, A. (Ed.), *Oxford Handbook of Archaeological Ceramic Analysis*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 101–113.
- Roux, V., 2019. *Ceramics and Society. A Technological Approach to Archaeological Assemblages*. Springer, Cham.
- Roux, V., 2020. Chaîne opératoire, technological networks and sociological interpretations. *Cuadernos De Prehistoria y Arqueología De La Universidad De Granada* 30, 15–34.
- Santacreu, D.A., 2014. *Materiality, Techniques and Society in Pottery Production. The Technological Study of Archaeological Ceramics through Paste Analysis*. De Gruyter Open Ltd, Warsaw/Berlin.
- Santacreu, D.A., 2017. Interpreting long-term use of raw materials in pottery production: A holistic perspective. *J. Archaeol. Sci. Rep.* 16, 505–512.
- Searle, D.L., 1969. The structural geology of the volcanic rocks south of Aradhiou and Politiko. *Bulletin of the Geological Survey Department* 2, 1–18.
- Sillar, B., Tite, M.S., 2000. The challenge of ‘technological choices’ for materials science approaches in archaeology. *Archaeometry* 42, 2–20.
- Sturm, C., Clark, J.K., Barton, L., 2016. The logic of ceramic technology in marginal environments: implications for mobile life. *Am. Antiq.* 81 (4), 645–663.
- Travé Allepez, E., 2021. Colour Transformation and Textural Change in Biotite: Some Remarks for the Interpretation of Firing Technology in Greyware Pottery Thin-Sections. *Minerals* 11 (428).
- Tykot, R.H., 2016. Using nondestructive portable X-ray fluorescence spectrometers on stone, ceramics, metals, and other materials in museums: Advantages and limitations. *Appl. Spectrosc.* 70 (1), 42–56.
- Wallace, S., 1995. *Recognising Change in Systems of Prehistoric Ceramic Production: A Statistical Approach to Identifying Standardisation in Ceramic Attributes, Applied at Kissonerga-Mosphilia Cyprus*. University of Edinburgh [Unpublished master dissertation].
- Webb, J., Frankel, D., Croft, P., McCartney, C., 2009. Excavations at Politiko-Kokkinorotsos. A Chalcolithic Hunting Station in Cyprus. *Proc. Prehist. Soc* 75, 189–237.
- Whitbread, I.K., 1986. The characterisation of argillaceous inclusions in ceramic thin sections. *Archaeometry* 28 (1), 79–88.
- Whitbread, I. K. (1995). *Greek transport amphorae: A petrological and archaeological study*. The British School at Athens. (Fitch Laboratory Occasional Paper, 4).